

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D7.1

Robotics system integration (first version)

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACK	Acknowledgement message
API	Application Programming Interface
ARUCO	Augmented Reality Universidad de COrdoba
CSV	Comma Separated Value
DC	Direct Current
DDHL	Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer
DLL	Dynamic Link Library
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
gRCS	Generic Robot Control Station
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
ID	Identifier
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IP	Internet Protocol (address)
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LED	Light Emitting Diode
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LOAM	LiDAR Odometry And Mapping
mRCS	Mission-specific Robot Control Station
NED	North-East-Down
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
PC	Personal Computer
PID	Proportional, Integral, Derivative (control)
PWM	Pulse-Width Modulation
RCS	Robot Control Station
ROS	Robot Operating System
SDK	Software Development Kit
UAL	UAV Abstraction Layer
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
USB	Universal Serial Bus

UWB	Ultra-Wide Band
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language
ZMQ	Zero Message Queue

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. INTRODUCTION

One of PILOTING's technological objectives is the integration of diverse robotic systems using open interfaces and a scalable architecture. The PILOTING Inspection & Maintenance (I&M) platform will be integrated with nine different types of robot vehicles and applied to three scenarios (refineries, bridges/viaducts, and tunnels).

Following the iterative and incremental development strategy, the project is split in two main phases, each one being a complete development cycle composed of design, development, integration, testing and evaluation. This deliverable details the integration of the robotic systems in the first of the two main cycles.

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This document is a description of the efforts that led to the integration of two key components of the PILOTING I&M platform:

- the generic Robot Control Station (gRCS), which standardizes the supervision of the robotic vehicles, and
- the robotic engine, which integrates the autonomous functionalities on the robotic vehicles.

It also includes experiments performed at laboratory or controlled environments, in order to validate such integration.

This deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within tasks T7.1 ("Ground and crawler robotic systems integration") and T7.2 ("Aerial and hybrid robotic system integration").

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the integration of the gRCS with the robotic vehicles, building on the messages and interfaces defined in D6.1 (General robot control station, first version).

Section 3 presents the integration of the autonomous functionalities for each of the robotic vehicles (robotic engine), as well as the communication with the gRCS.

Section 4 describes the experiments performed in controlled environments to validate the aforementioned integrations.

Finally, section 5 presents the conclusions and future work.

2. Generic Robot Control Station Integration

In the deliverable “D6.1 General robot control station (first version)” the communication interface used for data transfer between the robotic systems and the general robot control station was defined. Specifically, the message exchange sequences were detailed, as well as the content and format of said messages.

The following is a summary of the previously defined message exchange sequences.

- S1. Upload the waypoint list to the robotic system
Before starting a mission, the gRCS must send the waypoint list to the robotic system.
- S2. Download the waypoint list from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, it may be the case that the robotic system performs a re-planning of the waypoint list (for example, when an obstacle is encountered along the way). If this occurs, the gRCS has to request the modified waypoint list from the robotic system.
- S3. Download the checklist from the robotic system
Before starting the mission, the gRCS operator must perform a set of checks associated with the robotic system. To do this, the gRCS must have previously asked the robotic system for its checklist.
- S4. Download the list of alarms from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the gRCS can show the operator the status of a set of alarms predefined by the robotic system (for example, the battery level). To do this, the gRCS must have previously requested the robotic system for its alarm list.
- S5. Download the list of high-level actions from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the gRCS operator can command the robotic system a set of high-level actions. To do this, the gRCS must have previously asked the robotic system for its high-level action list.
- S6. Send commands to the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the gRCS operator can send commands to the robotic system (for example, the commands associated with high-level actions).
- S7. Receive pose from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the robotic system periodically sends its position and orientation to the gRCS, as well as the position and orientation of its sensors.
- S8. Receive alarm status from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the robotic system periodically sends to the gRCS the status of the alarms it has defined.
- S9. Receive message status from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the robotic system can send the gRCS descriptive messages of events that have occurred.
- S10. Set current waypoint item to the robotic system

Once the robotic system has received the waypoint list and the mission has started, the gRCS can command the robotic system a specific waypoint to reach.

- S11. Receive waypoint list progress from the robotic system
During the execution of the mission, the robotic system sends messages with the progress of the waypoint list.
- S12. Heartbeat protocol
The heartbeat protocol is used to advertise the existence of a system on the MAVLink network.

This section details the software developments carried out in this communications protocol in order to facilitate the integration work between the robotic systems and the gRCS addressed in this deliverable.

2.1 Integration approach

First, to implement the previously defined communication protocol, it is necessary to generate the specific MAVLink library. This library is created from a file with XML format, that must contain the definition of the content of the messages used in this communication interface, and using the source code generator tools provided with the MAVLink project. For this, the "mavgenerate" tool (which provides a graphical user interface) or the "mavgen" tool (which uses the command line) can be used. It should be noted that these tools allow the generation of source code for the main programming languages used in robotics, such as C, C++, C#, Java, Python, etc. The guide on how to use these tools can be found on the official website¹.

Once the MAVLink library in the necessary programming language has been generated, each of the systems at both ends of the communication interface must use it to implement each of the functionalities defined in the message exchange sequences, that is, using the corresponding messages as request or response at the appropriate time of each sequence.

2.1.1 PILOTING-MAVSDK

In order to facilitate the work of implementing the message exchange sequences, a library has been developed containing all these functionalities, called "PILOTING-MAVSDK". This library provides a simple and easy-to-use API that will allow each of the systems at both ends

¹ https://mavlink.io/en/getting_started/generate_libraries.html

of the communications interface not to have to develop their own implementation of the message exchange sequences, and thus not have to reinvent the wheel.

After surveying the programming languages used in the different systems considered in the PILOTING project, it was concluded that the majority used the C++ programming language. So, it was decided to implement the PILOTING-MAVSDK library in such language.

To implement this library, we have relied on the open-source library MAVSDK², making the necessary adaptations to add the functionalities defined in the message exchange sequences.

The PILOTING-MAVSDK library is divided into different modules, and each module contains an implementation to be used by the gRCS and another implementation to be used by the robotic system. The API obtained as a result of the development of the PILOTING-MAVSDK library is detailed below.

2.1.1.1 Waypoint list module

This module implements the message exchange sequences related to the waypoint list, which are the following:

- S1. Upload the waypoint list to the robotic system
- S2. Download the waypoint list from the robotic system
- S10. Set current waypoint item to the robotic system
- S11. Receive waypoint list progress from the robotic system

The following tables show the resulting API after implementing the message exchange sequences corresponding to this module.

gRCS	Robotic System
<p>upload_waypoint_list</p> <p>Upload a list of waypoint items to the robotic system. This function is blocking.</p>	<p>download_waypoint_list_async</p> <p>Prepare the robotic system to be able to download a list of waypoint items from the gRCS. This function is non-blocking.</p>
<p>upload_waypoint_list_async</p> <p>Asynchronously upload a list of waypoint items to the robotic system. This function is non-blocking.</p>	<p>send_download_ack</p> <p>Sends acknowledgment to finish a waypoint list download sequence. This function is blocking.</p>

² <https://mavsdk.mavlink.io/main/en/cpp/>

<p>cancel_waypoint_list_upload</p> <p>Cancel a waypoint list upload sequence in progress. This function is blocking.</p>	<p>cancel_waypoint_list_download</p> <p>Cancel a waypoint list download sequence in progress. This function is blocking.</p>
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Table 2. API for “S1. Upload the waypoint list to the robotic system”

gRCS	Robotic System
<p>download_waypoint_list</p> <p>Download a list of waypoint items from the robotic system. This function is blocking.</p>	<p>upload_waypoint_list_async</p> <p>Prepare the robotic system to be able to upload a list of waypoint items to the gRCS. This function is non-blocking.</p>
<p>download_waypoint_list_async</p> <p>Asynchronously download a list of waypoint items from the robotic system. This function is non-blocking.</p>	<p>set_upload_waypoint_list</p> <p>Sets the list of waypoint items to be uploaded to the gRCS. This function is blocking.</p>
<p>cancel_waypoint_list_download</p> <p>Cancel a waypoint list download sequence in progress. This function is blocking.</p>	<p>cancel_waypoint_list_upload</p> <p>Cancel a waypoint list upload sequence in progress. This function is blocking.</p>

Table 3 API for “S2. Download the waypoint list from the robotic system”

gRCS	Robotic System
<p>set_current_waypoint_list_item</p> <p>Indicate to the robotic system the index of the waypoint to be executed. By setting the current index to 0, the mission is restarted from the beginning. If it is set to a specific index of a waypoint item, the mission will be set to this item. This function is blocking.</p>	<p>subscribe_waypoint_list_set_current</p> <p>Subscribe to waypoint list set current command. The callback of this function must be answered immediately using the method 'update_current_waypoint_list_item'. This function is non-blocking.</p>

Table 4. API for “S11. Receive waypoint list progress from the robotic system”

gRCS	Robotic System
<p>subscribe_waypoint_list_progress</p> <p>Subscribe to waypoint list execution progress updates. This function is non-blocking.</p>	<p>update_current_waypoint_list_item</p> <p>Indicate to the gRCS the index of the waypoint that is currently executing. This function is blocking.</p>

<p>waypoint_list_progress</p> <p>Check the progress of the waypoint list execution.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>	<p>update_reached_waypoint_list_item</p> <p>Indicate to the gRCS the index of the waypoint that has just finished being executed.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>
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Table 5. API for “S10. Set current waypoint item to the robotic system”

2.1.1.2 Checklist module

This module implements the message exchange sequence related to the checklist, which is the following:

- S3. Download the checklist from the robotic system

The following table shows the resulting API after implementing the message exchange sequence corresponding to this module.

gRCS	Robotic System
<p>download_checklist</p> <p>Download a list of check items from the robotic system.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>	<p>upload_checklist_async</p> <p>Prepare the robotic system to be able to upload a list of check items to the gRCS.</p> <p>This function is non-blocking.</p>
<p>download_checklist_async</p> <p>Asynchronously download a list of check items from the robotic system.</p> <p>This function is non-blocking.</p>	<p>set_upload_checklist</p> <p>Sets the list of check items to be uploaded to the gRCS.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>
<p>cancel_checklist_download</p> <p>Cancel a checklist download sequence in progress.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>	<p>cancel_checklist_upload</p> <p>Cancel a checklist upload sequence in progress.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>

Table 6. API for “S3. Download the checklist from the robotic system”

2.1.1.3 Alarm list module

This module implements the message exchange sequences related to the alarm list, which are the following:

- S4. Download the list of alarms from the robotic system
- S8. Receive alarm status from the robotic system

The following tables show the resulting API after implementing the message exchange sequences corresponding to this module.

gRCS	Robotic System
download_alarm_list Download a list of alarm items from the robotic system. This function is blocking.	upload_alarm_list_async Prepare the robotic system to be able to upload a list of alarm items to the gRCS. This function is non-blocking.
download_alarm_list_async Asynchronously download a list of alarm items from the robotic system. This function is non-blocking.	set_upload_alarm_list Sets the list of alarm items to be uploaded to the gRCS. This function is blocking.
cancel_alarm_list_download Cancel an alarm list download sequence in progress. This function is blocking.	cancel_alarm_list_upload Cancel an alarm list upload sequence in progress. This function is blocking.

Table 7. API for “S4. Download the list of alarms from the robotic system”

gRCS	Robotic System
subscribe_alarm_status Subscribe to alarm status updates. This function is non-blocking.	send_alarm_status Indicate to the gRCS the status of an alarm. This function is blocking.

Table 8. API for “S8. Receive alarm status from the robotic system”

2.1.1.4 High-level action list module

This module implements the message exchange sequence related to the high-level action list, which is the following:

- S5. Download the list of high-level actions from the robotic system

The following table shows the resulting API after implementing the message exchange sequence corresponding to this module.

gRCS	Robotic System
download_hl_action_list Download a list of high-level action items from the robotic system. This function is blocking.	upload_hl_action_list_async Prepare the robotic system to be able to upload a list of high-level action items to the gRCS. This function is non-blocking.
download_hl_action_list_async Asynchronously download a list of high-level action items from the robotic system. This function is non-blocking.	set_upload_hl_action_list Sets the list of high-level action items to be uploaded to the gRCS. This function is blocking.

<p>cancel_hl_action_list_download</p> <p>Cancel a high-level action list download sequence in progress.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>	<p>cancel_hl_action_list_upload</p> <p>Cancel a high-level action list upload sequence in progress.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>
--	--

Table 9. API for “S5. Download the list of high-level actions from the robotic system”

2.1.1.5 Command module

This module implements the message exchange sequence related to the commands, which is the following:

- S6. Send commands to the robotic system

The following table shows the resulting API after implementing the message exchange sequence corresponding to this module.

gRCS	Robotic System
<p>send_command</p> <p>Send a command to the robotic system.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>	<p>subscribe_command</p> <p>Subscribe to commands.</p> <p>The callback must be answered immediately using the method 'send_command_ack'.</p> <p>This function is non-blocking.</p>
<p>send_command_async</p> <p>Asynchronously send a command to the robotic system.</p> <p>This function is non-blocking.</p>	<p>send_command_ack</p> <p>Indicate to the gRCS the response for a received command.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>
<p>cancel_send_command</p> <p>Cancel a command send sequence in progress.</p> <p>This function is blocking.</p>	

Table 10. API for “S6. Send commands to the robotic system”

2.1.1.6 Telemetry module

This module implements the message exchange sequences related to the telemetry, which are the following:

- S7. Receive pose from the robotic system
- S9. Receive message status from the robotic system

The following tables show the resulting API after implementing the message exchange sequences corresponding to this module.

gRCS	Robotic System
subscribe_position_velocity Subscribe to position and velocity updates. This function is non-blocking.	send_position_velocity Indicate to the gRCS the position and velocity of the robotic system. This function is blocking.
position_velocity Poll a position and velocity from the robotic system. This function is blocking.	
subscribe_attitude Subscribe to attitude updates. This function is non-blocking.	send_attitude Indicate to the gRCS the position and velocity of the robotic system. This function is blocking.
attitude Poll an attitude from the robotic system. This function is blocking.	

Table 11. API for “S7. Receive pose from the robotic system”

gRCS	Robotic System
subscribe_text_status Subscribe to events (in text format) updates. This function is non-blocking.	send_text_status Send a text message to the gRCS indicating an event that has occurred in the robotic system. This function is blocking.
text_status Poll an event (in text format) from the robotic system. This function is blocking.	

Table 12. API for “S9. Receive message status from the robotic system”

2.1.2 PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS

The main objective of the development of this abstraction layer is to simplify the use of PILOTING-MAVSDK. Most robotic vehicles run their algorithms using the ROS framework, so this interface will be used to send all the necessary information from the robot via the PILOTING-MAVSDK communication interface.

Before running the ROS node on the robotic vehicle, it is necessary to modify a configuration file. In this file, all the PILOTING-MAVSDK parameters can be found: IP addresses and ports, component and system identifiers, etc.

Next, the initialization process of the PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS node will be explained. This process is shown in Figure 1. First, the configuration file with the necessary parameters will be read. Using the local system identifiers, the PILOTING-MAVSDK object is created. After that, an attempt shall be made to establish a UDP connection to the target system. If this connection does not fail, and a UDP connection between hosts can be established, it will search for and connect to the system whose index is the target. Once connected to the system, the communication interfaces between ROS and PILOTING-MAVSDK shall be established.

Figure 1. PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS initialization

Below, the communication interfaces established between ROS and PILOTING-MAVSDK are discussed. These interfaces are implemented through ROS subscribers and services. Through the subscribers, information is taken from the robotic vehicle and sent via PILOTING-MAVSDK. For messages not found by default in ROS, custom message types have been created. The topics and message formats that are read can be seen in Figure 2. PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS Subscribers

ROS SUBSCRIBED TOPIC	ROS MESSAGE TYPE	MAVSDK PLUGIN
"/mavsdk_ros/alarm_status"	mavsdk_ros/AlarmStatus	AlarmRoboticVehicle
"/mavsdk_ros/local_position" or "/mavsdk_ros/local_position/pose" "/mavsdk_ros/local_position/twist"	nav_msgs/Odometry or geometry_msgs/PoseStamped geometry_msgs/TwistStamped	TelemetryRoboticVehicle
"/mavsdk_ros/text_status"	mavsdk_ros/TextStatus	TelemetryRoboticVehicle

Figure 2. PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS Subscribers

When the PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS node receives a message from subscribers, it transforms it into PILOTING-MAVSDK format and sends it using the associated plugin in each case. Using the topic `"/mavsdk_ros/alarm_status"`, the status of any of the alarms of the robotic vehicle can be reported, and these alarms are defined through a service. It is worth mentioning

the case of the telemetry of the robotic vehicle, as it can be sent in two ways: by using a ROS Odometry message, or by subscribing to the *PoseStamped* and the *TwistStamped* separately. The ROS node will take care of synchronizing the pose and twist to be sent by PILOTING-MAVSDK. Finally, the topic `"/mavsdk_ros/text_status"` is used to send any information to PILOTING-MAVSDK.

In the case of ROS services, these are used to configure the internal information of the robotic vehicle. This information includes, for example, the alarms associated with the vehicle, high-level actions, etc. These services are shown in Figure 3.

ROS SERVICES	ROS MESSAGE TYPE	MAVSDK PLUGIN
<code>"/mavsdk_ros/set_upload_alarms"</code>	AlarmItem[]	AlarmRoboticVehicle
<code>"/mavsdk_ros/set_upload_checklist"</code>	ChecklistItem[]	ChecklistRoboticVehicle
<code>"/mavsdk_ros/set_upload_hl_action"</code>	HLActionItem[]	HLActionRoboticVehicle
<code>"/mavsdk_ros/set_upload_waypoint_list"</code>	WaypointList	InspectionRoboticVehicle
<code>"/mavsdk_ros/update_current_waypoint_item"</code>	uint16_t	
<code>"/mavsdk_ros/update_reached_waypoint_item"</code>	uint16_t	

Figure 3. PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS Services

The services associated with alarms, checklists and high-level actions must be configured at the start-up of the robotic system, as the gRCS must know this information before starting the inspection.

Concerning the waypoint list service, it must be called every time the route loaded in the robotic vehicle is modified, as this informs the system of the modification, and the new route can then be requested from PILOTING-MAVSDK. Finally, the services associated with the current and reached waypoints shall be called during the execution of the inspection in order to update both the gRCS and the mRCS.

Some services are used to communicate the gRCS with the Mission Manager of the robotic vehicle. The server for these services must be in the Mission Manager, and they are called by PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS when a particular type of information is received from PILOTING-MAVSDK. This information includes the commands and the inspection to be performed:

- In the case of commands, when a command is sent by PILOTING-MAVSDK, it is received by this ROS node which calls the appropriate service, `"/mavsdk_ros/command"`. The Mission Manager then evaluates whether the command is valid or not, and replies with an ACK message.
- In the case of inspections, the service `"/masdk_ros/inspection"` is called when an inspection is requested to be uploaded from the gRCS. The Mission Manager evaluates if the inspection is valid and if it is possible to be uploaded to the robotic vehicle. After that, an ACK is sent informing if the upload was successful or if there was an error.

Figure 4 shows the workflow when the gRCS operator sends a command to the Mission Manager. The case of the inspection is analogous.

Figure 4. Communication between gRCS and Mission Manager

3. Robotic Engine Integration

In this section, we will proceed to describe the software integration of all robotic platforms through their robotic engines. This integration includes the software information implemented to operate the autonomous functionalities described in previous deliverables, as well as establishing a common communication with the gRCS for all platforms. This section does not intend to describe again the core of the autonomous functionalities, but to give information about their actual implementation performed for the experiments.

Each platform is described below, grouped by type: first the aerial robots, then ground robots, and finally crawlers and hybrid robots.

3.1 Aerial Robots

3.1.1 AEROX

The AEROX platform is the one in charge of performing the refinery inspection using a sensor that physically contacts the surface of the infrastructure. This section describes the software designed and integrated into the robotic engine.

The picture below shows the main block diagram with all the systems and connections between them.

Figure 5. Block diagram of AEROX's platform

As it can be seen in the previous figure, the onboard computer centralizes the processing, reading all the sensors, and executing all the processes. In short, it integrates the robotic engine.

The integration of all the software has been done using ROS, which facilitates the development of processes, known as nodes, and the communications between them through topics and services.

The integration performed for each of the nodes running the AEROX robotic engine is detailed below.

- **State Machine**

The submodule “State Machine” refers to the software designed to manage the different states through which the system can pass. The following diagram shows an overview of the states of which it is composed.

Figure 6. AEROX Main state machine diagram flow

The “Idle” state is where the system is while it is on the ground waiting to start the mission, and also the state to which it goes once the aircraft has landed. While in this state, the necessary system checks are carried out, and the route to be followed and the desired point of contact are generated.

The “Manual” state is the state in which the safety pilot has full control of the aircraft and oversees taking off and contacting the surface to be inspected. This is because this is not a commercial aircraft and there are these two critical points of the mission that must be performed by an expert pilot.

The “Go Waypoint” state is where the system goes to the point to be inspected indicated by the operator in an autonomous way, performing the navigation using GPS.

“Contact” state is the state that the system goes to once the pilot has contacted the surface to be inspected. At that moment, by pressing a button, the system switches to autonomous contact mode.

“Go Home” state is the state in which, after the corresponding measurements have been taken, the aircraft returns autonomously to the take-off point, again using GPS.

The complete process of a mission consists of the following steps:

1. Take-off and stabilization of the aircraft by the pilot.
2. Flight in autonomous mode to a point close to the area to be inspected selected by the operator.
3. Return to manual mode to perform the approach and contact with the surface to be inspected.
4. Switch to contact mode, where the system returns to autonomous mode and performs solid displacements to the end effector while maintaining perpendicularity to the contact surface.
5. Once the inspection is complete, the safety pilot performs the surface separation maneuver.
6. Finally, the aircraft moves to the return-to-home state, where the aircraft autonomously returns to the take-off point.

- **Joystick Bridge**

The UAV is operated through the command of a pilot who, looking at data available, gives references to the control system through a joystick to make the aerial robot operate correctly. For this reason, a bridge has been implemented to exchange data between the joystick and the system.

- **Servos Bridge**

The servos located in the robotic arm exchange data with the embedded PC. Their position data, measured through encoders, is necessary to estimate the position of the whole arm, and a specific signal to move the arm is sent to them. For these reasons, a communication bridge has been designed for the proper function of the system.

- **DJI Bridge**

In order to establish communication with the aircraft's autopilot (DJI A3), a software bridge has been implemented. This communication is wired between the autopilot and the onboard computer.

It is important to note that to send and receive the autopilot inputs, it is necessary to serialize or deserialize the messages. For this purpose, a modified version of the ROS OnBoard SDK is used. This is written in C++ and creates an interface to the SDK functionalities by using ROS topics, services or messages.

Thanks to this, it will be possible to send the aircraft's movement instructions, and allow the safety modules developed to be connected to the aircraft so that the flight status and telemetry can be always known.

- **Camera Drivers**

AEROX's inspections are carried out with the usage of visual images to provide feedback to the safety pilot and the operator, and to provide useful data within the inspection operation. For that, the onboard camera needs to send images to give visual feedback to the operator, and data from images to provide information on the inspection operation.

- **Telemetry Bridge**

Useful data are received by the pilot during the AEROX flight to provide feedback on the UAV behavior and its operativity. The telemetry bridge block is responsible to collect the data from the system and send it to the gRCS.

- **Relative Position Estimator**

The pose estimator sub-block is a software development that receives the information from the sensors and calculates the reference position that the aircraft must reach in order to maintain perpendicularity with the contact surface. To do this, it uses the information of the angles of each of the aircraft's degrees of freedom, provided by the sensor driver, and the inverse kinematics equation of the UAV/arm system.

- **UAV Control**

The PID control subplot is a script compiled using MATLAB, which is responsible for the computation of the control action to make the aerial robot reach the prescribed position and orientation. A scheme of its structure is presented in figure 3, the error signal is computed by comparing the reference signal with the current data received from the platform. The reference signal can be the input given directly by the pilot ("Manual" mode) or a signal generated by the system ("Contact" mode). The structure is made of a standard PID control structure, as shown in Figure 7, but some developments have been considered with respect to it.

Figure 7. Scheme of PID control architecture

Firstly, the reset dynamics are added to the integral action; this allows the system to get faster response and to avoid the divergence of the integral part of the control action under unexpected situations. Further development has been considered for the derivative action; a filter block has been added to the input signal to the derivative block to smooth the derivative control action. The control signal generated by the PID is then saturated to avoid too large values to inject into the rotors of the system, which could cause severe failures.

In terms of communication with the gRCS, the onboard computer uses the MAVSDK-ROS and several ROS topics and services for this. There is a long list of communication data between the UAV and the gRCS, but perhaps the most important one could be the waypoint service, which receives information about the inspection point selected by the operator, and the live position service, which provides the gRCS with the UAV's position at all times.

3.1.2 AERO-CAM

The AERO-CAM platform is the one devoted to performing visual inspections on viaducts. This section describes the software designed and integrated into its robotic engine.

Figure 8 shows the general diagram of the blocks implemented in the robotic engine. On the left, those marked in green are sensors or external data that are connected to the platform. AERO-CAM has two onboard computers, an Intel NUCi7 and a Raspberry Pi, which are communicated through a local onboard switch and have their internal clocks synchronized.

Figure 8. AERO-CAM general diagram block

The processes running inside the onboard computers make use of ROS to facilitate communication between them through topics and services. On the other hand, communication with the gRCS shown on the right is done using the MAVSDK library, which manages the connection through sockets.

The following is the integration of the general diagram, expanding each of the blocks:

- **Ouster LiDAR driver**

It is necessary to have a driver module that transforms the UDP packages sent by the Ouster LiDAR in a ROS message. The main purpose of this module is to obtain the full point cloud provided by the LiDAR in a format that can be easily understood inside our framework.

The raw LiDAR data consists of many range measurements made by multiple spinning lasers, which this module converts into a point cloud data type. More specifically, our node transforms this raw data into a *sensor_msgs/PointCloud2* ROS message.

- **DJI Bridge**

As with the previous platform, in order to establish communication with the aircraft's autopilot (DJI A3), a software bridge has been implemented. This communication is wired between the autopilot and the onboard computer.

For this purpose, a modified version of the ROS OnBoard SDK is used. This is written in C++ and creates an interface to the SDK functionalities by using ROS topics, services or messages. Thanks to this, it will be possible to send the aircraft's movement instructions, and allow the safety modules developed to be connected to the aircraft so that the flight status can be always known.

- **Gimbal Driver**

To establish communications with the gimbal, a ROS node has been developed using the SDK provided by the manufacturer Gremsy. The gimbal is connected via a USB serial cable, so the node opens communications and starts deserializing incoming gimbal sensor messages. The gimbal sends the position of each of its axes, as well as its mode, status, etc. The node receives these positions and publishes them in ROS topics. In addition, to facilitate integration with the rest of the system, it publishes the coordinate frames of these positions. In this way, the system finds the exact transform of the gimbal position for a given instant.

The node is also able to receive the desired position from the gimbal and is responsible for serializing and sending it. As for the implementation, it is programmed in C++ language.

- **Relative Localization**

The purpose of this block is to estimate the transformation (translation and rotation) of AERO-CAM's base frame from its take-off location, based on onboard sensor readings without using any external infrastructure or prior data. It mainly makes use of the onboard 3D LiDAR and a 9-axis IMU in a tightly-coupled strategy for sensor fusion, in order to estimate the UAV position and orientation at each instant. The algorithm operates in real-time at a high frequency (400 Hz) to provide the UAV Control block with accurate localization feedback to ensure a stable flight while navigating autonomously to the desired target waypoints.

- **Global Localization**

AERO-CAM can locate itself from the take-off position thanks to the odometry. However, it is necessary to globally localize it within a map. We need to know where the inspection points of the map are located in order to generate the correct waypoints to navigate to them. The only transform which is unknown is the pose between the odometry origin and the map origin.

To achieve that, we use the LiDAR point cloud and the map point cloud in order to solve the problem known as point clouds registration. Therefore, the inputs to this module are the two points clouds, and optionally an initial guess in case this information is available.

- **Telemetry Bridge**

This submodule has been developed to translate AERO-CAM's estimated pose (position and orientation) from a local to a global reference frame. The UAV Control block calculates the reference position using local references to the robot frame; however, visualization tools such

as the gRCS need the robot pose in global coordinates referenced to a map, so a node that converts the poses and velocities is needed. To achieve this goal, this node uses the transformation information between the odometry frame and the map frame calculated by the Global Localization submodule.

- **Sony Camera Bridge**

In order to carry out a visual inspection using AERO-CAM, it is necessary to be able to take pictures in specific locations. The hardware used to take the pictures is a Sony Alpha 7 Mark III, which can be remotely controlled from a host PC using the Camera Remote SDK provided by Sony Company. Essentially, Sony Camera Bridge is a ROS wrapper of the Sony SDK library, allowing the following functionalities:

1. Take a picture when it is requested.
2. Save a picture in a predefined folder.
3. Publish the metadata of a saved picture.
4. Get/set camera properties such as ISO, aperture and shutter speed.

Every time this node is executed, a folder named with the current date is created in order to save the pictures there. The name of this folder can be requested by other submodules through a ROS service. When Sony Camera Bridge is asked to take a picture and it has been successfully taken using the SDK, the picture metadata is published. The Sony SDK library allows the user to know exactly the timestamp when the photo was taken. Using this information, the Sony Camera Bridge is able to look up the transformation from the camera to the map at that moment, being aware of the pose of the acquired picture. The Sony Camera Bridge assigns a unique id to each picture.

- **Camera Picture Projection**

This module estimates the distance from the camera to the closest object in the map, taking into account the camera position and orientation. The Camera Picture Projection receives the picture metadata of each photo from the Sony Camera Bridge submodule, which includes the pose of the photo taken. Using this information and the map, the Camera Picture Projection can estimate the distance to the object under inspection. Moreover, using the camera parameters and the data mentioned before, this submodule can also estimate the ratio mm/pixel of each picture.

The distance and the mm/pixel ratio are added to the picture metadata of each picture, and all this information is republished.

- **State Machines**

In this section, the developments made for managing the aircraft's flight and mission are described. A diagram showing the workflow is shown in Figure 9. The first interface is the *DJI Safety Manager*, which manages the aircraft's authority and the verification that all the

necessary information for the autonomous mission is received correctly. If during the execution of the autonomous mission, any problem occurs that compromises the mission (e.g. relative localization drift), it will be responsible for returning the authority of the aircraft to the safety pilot.

Figure 9. Flight State Machines diagram block

Then, there are the flight state machines. These will inform and manage the status of the aircraft. In addition, they allow the performance of autonomous functions, such as the management of mission waypoints and the transformation of the mission between global and local reference frames. The communication interfaces are ROS services. There are two state machines:

- DJI Main State Machine allows the most basic flight tasks to be carried out, such as taking off or landing the aircraft. In addition, it manages between different flight modes when the aircraft is in the air; auto, offboard and assisted. In the auto state, the autonomous mission will be managed, as well as the whole transformation between local and global reference frames. As for the assisted state, the aim is to be able to move the aircraft using a joystick or a simulator. Finally, during the development of AERO-CAM, the offboard state does not need to be used as it is designed to perform high-level tasks. It should be noted that it is possible to switch to a manual state from any state, as the safety pilot can request it when he/she considers it necessary.
- DJI Auto State Machine handles the control references that are sent to the MATLAB Control submodule, as well as the transformation between reference systems in the waypoints of the mission from a known "home" position. In addition, it manages the pre-landing status to ensure a safe landing using an onboard altimeter. It allows to start the autonomous mission, pause it, or, if necessary, send the UAV to a specific waypoint to perform a measurement again.

Finally, the MATLAB Control module is a control strategy implemented on top of the DJI autopilot, as shown in Figure 9. This controller reads the estimated pose in local coordinates by the localization algorithm, and the control reference generated by the state machine. This controller communicates directly with the autopilot.

- **Mission Data Logger**

During the inspection, the robotic vehicle must be able to save all data related to the sensors to be available afterwards. The Mission Data Logger saves GPS telemetry data obtained from the DJI Autopilot, the localization telemetry data obtained from the UAV Control, and the picture metadata obtained from the Sony Camera Bridge; all these data are saved in CSV format. The Mission Data Logger also receives information about the folder where the pictures are saved, and creates a preview photo of reduced resolution, to be available for download and visualization in the mRCS.

Moreover, a text file in JSON format is generated, which includes the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. It contains the sensor list, the physical offset between sensors as they are mounted on the aircraft, as well as inspection information (e.g. the Inspection Plan Id). The configuration data of this file can be easily modified by the operator using the mRCS. In addition, the mission data logger creates an FTP server for two goals:

- download all the data after the execution of an inspection using an FTP client, and
- download the preview image and add the picture metadata for visualization on the mRCS during the execution of the inspection mission.

After the execution of the inspection, a folder with all the data is stored in order to be downloaded. The folder name includes the inspection plan id and the date and time of the execution. All the data described is organized as in the following folder structure.

Figure 10. Mission Results folder diagram

- **Mission Manager**

The mission manager submodule creates an interface between the general inspection functionalities and AERO-CAM’s specific functionalities. The general overview of the context of this submodule is shown in the following diagram.

Figure 11. Mission Manager diagram block

The Mission Manager also converts the planned path sent from the gRCS to a specific waypoint list. For this purpose, we use the parser submodule. If the waypoint type is an inspection point, the parser, using the asset information, calculates the plane where the original waypoint is and the normal direction to the plane. The corresponding generated specific waypoint position is separated from the plane by a distance given by a configuration parameter in the normal direction. If the waypoint type is an inspection area, the procedure is similar but creates a waypoint list to cover the area with a predefined minimum distance between waypoints. The conversion of an inspection area waypoint to the specific waypoint can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Specific Waypoint list detail

Then, the sequencer submodule from Mission Manager is the one responsible for keeping track of the navigation status of the UAV, and also for informing about changes of the on-board systems to the gRCS via MAVSDK_ROS.

Finally, the Mission Manager is also responsible for requesting the Mission Data Logger to start and stop logging mission data. Moreover, when a picture is taken by Sony Camera Bridge, it also informs the mRCS about this event.

3.1.3 VIAD-DRONE

The VIAD-DRONE is designed to solve three different use cases in the viaduct scenario: the bearing visual inspection, the sensor box installation, and the target installation. The proposed solution is a modular design, in which the same base platform can be adapted with some accessories to fulfill the specific needs of each use case. Specifically, the following add-ons are used for each use case:

- Bearing inspection: gimbal, inspection camera, and caterpillar system.
- Sensor box installation: caterpillar system and cargo system.
- Target installation: manipulator for target installation.

All the mentioned add-ons need dedicated drivers to control them, except for the manipulator for target installation which is a passive device. That is why it does not appear in the diagrams below.

Figure 13 shows the general block diagram of the implementation of the robotic engine. Green blocks represent external devices directly connected to the onboard computer via USB or indirectly connected via a network. The onboard computer is an Intel NUCi7. An Arduino Nano is used to handle the electronics of the caterpillar and cargo systems and the inspection camera.

Figure 13. VIAD-DRONE general block diagram

The blue blocks represent processes running inside the onboard computer, communicating through ROS topics and services. Communication with the gRCS is done using the MAVSDK ROS module, already explained in this deliverable.

The following details the insights of each block:

- **2D LiDAR driver**

This driver handles the communication with the 2D LiDAR via USB, reading the measurements and publishing them in ROS messages. More specifically, this module sends the LiDAR data in a *sensor_msgs/LaserScan* ROS message.

- **Navigation Cameras driver**

This module handles the communication with the navigation cameras. Its objective is to obtain images at the specified rate (30Hz) and publish them in *sensor_msgs/Image* ROS messages.

- **Gimbal driver**

This module is responsible for interfacing with the Gremsy gimbal, which is connected via USB to the onboard computer. It receives the commands and uses the Gremsy SDK to send them to the gimbal. At the same time, it is continuously reading the status of the gimbal, i.e., the position of each axis, and publishing this status in a ROS topic.

- **Add-ons ROS bridge**

This module communicates the ROS messages from the rest of the system with the add-ons driver running on the Arduino Nano, connected via USB to the onboard computer. More specifically, it reads the status of the add-ons (e.g., if the cargo system is opened or closed, the current velocity of each of the caterpillars) and sends commands to the connected add-ons (e.g., open/close the cargo system, set velocities for the caterpillar system, or take a picture).

- **Add-ons driver**

This module runs on the Arduino Nano board. On one hand, it communicates with the add-ons ROS bridge by a custom serial protocol. On the other hand, it interacts with the different add-ons (i.e., the cargo system, the caterpillar system, and the inspection camera) using PWM signals. As specified in deliverable D4.1, the inspection camera uses a Seagull #REC camera controller, which allows the control of the camera via PWM signals.

- **Localization**

This block is responsible for estimating the pose of the robot in the viaduct. It receives the measurements of the navigation sensors from their corresponding drivers, plus the IMU and GNSS data coming from the autopilot through the MAVROS module. This pose is then published in a *geometry_msgs/PoseStamped* ROS message to the rest of the system.

- **MAVROS**

This is an open-source module developed by the MAVLink community to translate the MAVLink protocol to ROS. In this case, MAVROS handles the serial interface with the autopilot, providing a set of ROS topics and services.

- **UAL**

This is also an open-source module, this time developed by USE in previous projects. UAL stands for UAV Abstraction Layer, as it is able to work with different autopilot firmware. This module allows a simpler interface to control the autopilot with MAVROS. Particularly, it eases the change of flight mode, provides simple services for taking-off, landing and going to a waypoint, and also provides position and velocity control of the robot. At the same time, it receives multiple information from the autopilot, while ensuring the safety of some procedures.

- **Action Server**

This module is in charge of executing the high-level actions received from the Mission Manager, while keeping the last updated with the status of these actions. As its name, it works as a ROS Action Server, providing access to a set of ROS actions to be executed. ROS actions are a special case of ROS communication interface, which combines topics and services to provide a simple mechanism to run actions that might take a long time to fulfill, keeping periodic feedback and notifying when it is completed.

Some high-level actions can be divided into smaller actions so when the first one is requested, many of these small ones are executed sequentially or in parallel.

In this case, the available high-level actions are the following:

- Take-off.
- Land.
- Go to waypoint.
- Go home.
- Attach to the ceiling.
- Crawl to waypoint.
- Inspect bearing.
- Install sensor box.
- Install target.

- **Mission Manager**

This is the core of the presented architecture. It maintains the communication link with the gRCS via the MAVSDK ROS module. From this link, it receives the mission data and the start/stop commands, among others. This is a complex module that can be divided into three parts or submodules, each one corresponding to a phase of the mission:

1. **Parser.** Interprets the messages received from the gRCS, i.e., waypoints or commands. Depending on the message, it triggers the corresponding functionality. For instance, receiving a set of waypoints triggers the Planner.
2. **Planner.** The VIAD-DRONE missions consist of a small set of inspection waypoints, like where to place the sensor box, which bearing to inspect, or where to install the target. The Planner uses this information, together with the initial position of the robot and the map of the viaduct and the environment to generate a plan composed of high-level actions as described in the Action Server.
3. **Execution manager.** It is responsible for handling the execution of the mission, by activating the planned actions calling the Action Server. It starts, pauses, resumes, and stops the missions while monitoring the execution and notifying the gRCS of any relevant event.

This module handles the communication with the navigation cameras. Its objective is to obtain images at the specified rate (30Hz) and publish them in *sensor_msgs/Image* ROS messages. In this case, the cameras are configured to capture the LEDs installed in the CART.

- **Tether driver**

The TTDRONE has the particularity of being linked to the ground robot with a tether, which provides power to increase the flight time. This tether system is an Elistair SAFE-T 2, which has an API to read the status (e.g., the power consumption) and send commands (e.g., increase/decrease the tension of the cable). This driver then provides a ROS interface for the rest of the system to know the status of the device and to control it.

- **Localization**

This block is responsible for estimating the pose of the robot in the tunnel. It receives the measurements of the navigation sensors from their corresponding drivers, plus the IMU data coming from the autopilot through the MAVROS module. In this case, it uses two navigation cameras (one pointing backwards and one pointing downwards) to detect the LEDs installed in the CART, a 2D LiDAR to detect the transversal plane of the tunnel, and a UWB sensor to measure the distance to the CART. Finally, the first relative estimation is transformed using the CART's pose estimation to obtain the global localization of the TTDRONE. This pose is then published in a *geometry_msgs/PoseStamped* ROS message to the rest of the system.

- **Action Server**

This module works like the one in the VIAD-DRONE. The only difference is that it has new available high-level actions:

- Take-off from the ground robot.
- Land on the ground robot.
- Emergency landing on the ground.
- Inspect tunnel defect.

- **Mission Manager**

This module is also the same that the one described for the VIAD-DRONE. The only difference for this case is that the Planner has its own implementation to solve the tunnel local inspection.

3.2 Ground Robots

3.2.1 *RISING and CART*

Robotnik is developing two different robotic platforms for the PILOTING project. The two of them will be used for inspection and maintenance in the project’s pilots. Both integrate the required sensors to perform those tasks. In Figure 15, the generic and specific components of both robots are shown and their connections. It also includes the particular components that are only in one of the two robots; either the RISING or the RBCart.

Figure 15. Components scheme for RISING and CART platforms

Both robots’ software is completely based on the ROS framework. This enables optimal communication between the hardware’s drivers and the control algorithms of perception, localization, and navigation. Those three main blocks of the robot’s Software contain various ROS nodes that are in charge of executing programs that communicate with each other collaborating between the different algorithms.

Figure 16. Ground robot's software blocks

Each robot has an upper software layer that controls the robot's overall state by monitoring the different sensors and actuators involved in the systems, the Robot Local Control.

Figure 17. Ground robot's software structure

This layer is a ROS node that follows a state machine in charge of allowing a good performance of the required tasks. The different elements involved in the overall system should be firstly initialized, constantly checked, and maintained in Ready State while no error has been detected. If an overridable error is detected, the robot will be in an emergency state until this is monitored to be back in an acceptable state. If the error es unrecoverable or should be manually checked out, the robot will stay in a Failure state until manually configured and repaired.

Figure 18. Robot local control state machine

The robotic engine integration when it comes to Robotnik’s ground robots has started from the adoption of MAVSDK wrapper and existing developments for the robots. It is important to remark that ROS system is always present within the developments, a fact that is fostering the integration activities.

With slight differences, the integration activities are valid for both RISING and CART vehicles due to them having the same underlying ROS-based software.

A short schema of the interactions is shown in the following figure.

Figure 19. Block diagram for RISING and CART platforms

What has been described as a “New Command Interface” is the middle step between the MAVSDK-ROS wrapper and the Robotnik’s Command Manager proprietary node.

First of all, an Interpreter node had to be developed in order to parse the information embedded in the MAVSDK message. Then, our solution was writing plain text commands in a YAML file in such a way that is understandable by the ROB Command Manager.

In this case, different mission plans can be recorded in a single YAML file that will be read by the Command Manager anytime. The system is even able to trigger past accomplished mission plans with just the instruction and the plan ID provided through the MAVLink protocol.

Figure 20. YAML file generated with inspection plan information

The Interpreter will also relate the exposed robot API with the command instructions in the gRCS and take care of calling ROS services, publishing ROS topics, or interfacing with the Command Manager when needed. Apart from that, the specific feedback coming from the robot status and mission execution has been implemented in the same Interpreter node.

A short mention to the Command Manager, which enables a higher-level interface that deals with the lower-level nodes of the robot. Robotnik’s Command Manager gives easy access to monitor the robot status (battery, motors, networks...) and to command actions (navigation, charging, trigger camera...).

Regarding the ROB Controllers Interaction, this is just a generic wording for grouping the different robot components at a lower level. Coming from the ROS structure, several packages are subscribed to different ROS topics and publish others, so that the robotic vehicle performs as expected. Within these packages, we are counting not only proprietary packages created by Robotnik, but also some of the widely used stacks in the open-source community. This is the case of different tools such as part of the navigation stack responsible for the robot’s basic movements, or the sensor feedback.

Different tests have been performed to evaluate the chain of nodes described in Figure 19. Those were escalating in complexity to validate the overall system. First of all, the heartbeat protocol was tested between the ROS and MAVLink environments. This was performed in a simulation of a standard Robotnik robot interpreting the various example scripts developed by CATEC (Figure 21). The programmed commands of navigation were properly executed and during these tests, the telemetry was monitored and transferred through MAVLink. This way, the exchange of information between the two parts was validated.

Figure 21. Screenshot with Robotnik's simulation using the MAVLink information exchange

On the other hand, it is important to remark that ROS architecture makes it easy to seamlessly change some of the controllers with minimum effort, looking for better performance or new functionalities. This is the case of new advanced functionalities developed by ETHZ and SINTEF to be integrated into both RISING and CART. The new abilities on skilled manipulation and specific environment navigation are to replace and complement other components in the same architecture. This is the reason for maintaining the ROS basic publisher-subscriber system while keeping some of the gRCS related interaction within the Interpreter tool explained before.

Specific details on the messages consumed by the advanced functionalities are described in the following subsections.

RISING system

- Autonomous Manipulation

The manipulator must reliably detect and manipulate hand-wheel valves, as the ones that are traditionally located in refinery plants to adapt to the flow pressure. This is a task peculiar to this use case and thus requires a mission-specific high-level command that is parsed and interpreted by the robotic vehicle in the corresponding manipulation command. The robotic engine uploads a list of high-level commands associated with a description as defined in `HL_ACTION_LIST_ITEM`. The `id MAV_CMD_COMPONENT_ARM_DISARM` is associated with the manipulation task. The `name` field is used to indicate the desired opening or closing angle of the valve. The `name` string is informing the robotic engine about the desired opening/closing angle. Notice that this is a sub-optimal approach as one would have to know in advance what that means in terms of pressure change in the pipe. However, there is currently too little information and data to devise a general perception system that can sense and record pressure changes. Nevertheless, this message can be easily modified in a later stage to account for different specifications, for example, desired pressure changes.

In order to manipulate the object, an approximate position needs to be known in the pre-recorded map. The gRCS is responsible for sending a corresponding command which specifies the approximate position and orientation (in quaternion format) of the object. The robotic engine validates the content of the message and computes a waypoint plan to reach the goal. This is then uploaded to the gRCS, by updating a concurrent inspection plan or creating a new one.

- Perception for Manipulation

We develop a perception module to triangulate the exact location of the valve in the robot local reference frame and generate a manipulation plan. The `TEXT_STATUS` message is sent to inform the gRCS of the errors and events that can occur during manipulation and perception and the current manipulation status (engaged, in progress, done). Errors are also propagated using the available Alarm message.

Figure 22. A visualization of the messages consumed by the manipulation autonomous functionality

CART system

The CART ground robot is integrated with an external sensor module for navigation in a tunnel without GNSS coverage. The sensor module contains LiDAR, IMU and camera that are used for localization of the vehicle in the tunnel. The sensor pack will be connected to the vehicle by Ethernet. The vehicle will also supply the sensor pack with 24V DC power. The sensor pack is planned to be mounted forward facing on the roof of the vehicle. It will rely on the light from the vehicle and will therefore be placed such that there are good enough light conditions for the localization camera to work in the tunnel scenario.

The localization algorithm is based on an extension of LOAM but adds point correspondences based on visual features (today ARUCO markers) to the ICP-based scan matching. The inclusion of visual features will make LiDAR odometry more robust to self-similar scans, and also allow us to more robustly re-localize in parts of the tunnel where unique visual features are present.

The localization module is integrated into ROS and will publish pose estimates that will be used by the ROS navigation stack on the CART robot. The data from the sensor module will be published via ROS topics which the ROB controller can use to get an accurate location during the inspection in a tunnel. In addition, the sensor pack will generate point cloud data that can be used in the creation of an initial map of the tunnel, which can then be reused during inspection sessions.

3.3 Crawlers and Hybrid Robots

3.3.1 BIKE

The BIKE control software already features localization functionalities with the so-called 3D LOC system. The PILOTING software layer receives the pose information from the 3D LOC part and sends steering signals to it.

Figure 23 shows the basic building blocks involved in the communication with the gRCS, as well as for executing the autonomous functionalities of the BIKE crawler.

Figure 23. BIKE communication links and modules

The Robot Control consists of a Bridge Program which handles all communications with the gRCS over the MAVLink protocol using a version of the MAVSDK library compiled for Windows. The execution of the autonomous functionalities is implemented in the Python submodule of the Robot Control. Internal communication with the Bridge Program uses ZMQ and Message Pack for serialization. The Python code calls DLLs for time-critical functionalities, and communicates with the BIKE Control over a WTR-specific ZMQ protocol.

- **Bridge Program**

The Bridge Program is implemented in C++ and it makes use of the MAVSDK library compiled for Windows. The bridge translates all commands received from the gRCS to the ZMQ by serializing via Message Pack. It also does the inverse.

Upon request from the gRCS, the Bridge Program sends the static elements such as the alarm list, the checklist items and the high-level actions to the gRCS.

- **State Machine**

The state machine governs the correct order of operations for retrieving and sending data from and to the gRCS and the BIKE Control. Furthermore, it handles the loading of the correct environment model (or previous mission) based on the Inspection Plan Identifier (*plan_id*) provided alongside the waypoint list from the gRCS.

Figure 24 shows the process for receiving a waypoint list and plan identifier and looking up the correct environment model (or an already existing mission file). If the model or mission file was found the waypoint list is checked and both, model/mission and waypoints are forwarded to the BIKE Control software.

Figure 24. Retrieving Waypoint List and Environment Model based on Inspection Plan identifier (plan_id) or Reloading/Resuming an existing Mission

- **Robot Localization System**

The 3D LOC robot localization system makes use of a 2D scanning LiDAR and a mesh model of the environment (typically a confined space). Once the robot is put into the confined space, an initial placement step by the operator is required. When operating through the gRCS, this step needs to be triggered after the waypoint list and plan identifier were successfully transmitted to the robot. A dedicated High-Level action is used. Once this action is sent to the robot, the 3D LOC software prompts the operator to perform the Robot Placement. If it is successful, a corresponding message is sent to the gRCS. Telemetry data can now be relayed to the gRCS and the path follower program activated. Figure 25 shows the process for placing the robot at the beginning of the work.

Figure 25. BIKE placement in 3D LOC

The 3D LOC system uses the coordinate system as used for generating the environment model. The telemetry data is sent to the gRCS following the NED (North-East-Down) convention. The state machine handles the coordinate transformation prior to transmitting the telemetry to the Bridge Program.

Figure 26. Left: Coordinate System of Environment Model; Right: NED coordinate system used for telemetry

The list of alarms (Table 13), the checklist items (Table 14) and the high-level actions (Table 15) are sent on request from the Bridge Program to the gRCS. Table 16 shows the messages used to communicate the robot state to the operator on gRCS.

ID	Name	Description
----	------	-------------

1	BAD_PLACEMENT	Robot placement failed; no valid pose information is available; Repeat placement
2	BAD_LIDAR	No LIDAR data available
3	BAD_IMU	No IMU data available
4	COM_FAULT	Communication with robot is/was interrupted
5	TORQUE	At least one motor reached the torque limit
6	TEMPERATURE	The internal temperature of the robot reached critical limit
7	GIMBAL_LIMIT	The gimbal axis reached mechanical limit

Table 13. BIKE list of alarms

ID	Check List Item	Description
1	CABLE LENGTH	Check if umbilical cable has sufficient slack for the mission and is otherwise properly secured and guided
2	SAFETY LINE	For Top-Deployments: Check safety line attachment and potential handling
3	COUPLANT SUPPLY	Check if reservoir is filled and pump is ready
4	CONFIGURATION	Check if the installed configuration matches the mission profile.

Table 14. BIKE Check-list Items

ID	Name	MAV Cmd and ENUM	Desc
1	PLACE_ROBOT	MAV_CMD_DO_SET_MODE	0: indicating that placement is needed / happening
2	PAUSE	MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE	0: Pause mission
3	RESUME	MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE	1: Continue mission
4	CAPTURE	MAV_CMD_IMAGE_START_CAPTURE	Capture Image from Inspection Camera

Table 15. BIKE list of High-Level Actions

ID	Name	MESSAGE Text
1	WAITING_FOR_PLACEMENT_MSG	“Robot requires placement. Complete placement process on robot interface!”
2	BAD_PLACEMENT_MSG	“Robot was not placed successfully in asset! “

3	GOOD_PLACEMENT_MSG	“Robot successfully placed and is now ready to start the mission.”
4	NO_MISSION	“The robot can not perform the required task. No mission is loaded or mission loading failed!”
5	BAD_MISSION_IDENTIFIER	“The mission identifier did not match a model or a mission on the robot control system!”
6	GOOD_WP_LIST_UPLOAD	“The waypoints were successfully loaded”
7	WAITING_CAPTURE	“Capture needs to be taken. Complete capture process on robot interface!”
8	CAPTURE_TAKEN	“Capture successfully stored in the mission database.”
9	CAPTURE_FAILED	“Capture was not stored successfully in the mission database!”
10	WAYPOINT_LIST_LOADED	“The waypoints were successfully loaded.”
11	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID	“The waypoints have been checked for consistency and are invalid.”
12	AUTOPILOT_STATE	“The autopilot is active/paused/inactive.”
13	NO_WAYPOINTS	“Autopilot cannot run because no waypoints are set.”

Table 16. BIKE list of messages

- **Robot Navigation**

The navigation module contains a Path Planner and a Path Follower. The Path Planner is invoked first with the list of waypoints received from the gRCS. The planner generates additional waypoints connecting the ones received from the gRCS when required. The planner is able to find the shortest path along a surface (as already described in section 3.2.2 of D5.2). The output of this planner is an enhanced waypoint list containing all waypoints in the correct order.

The Path Follower module receives the enhanced waypoint list and effectively controls the BIKE robot by converting robot pose updates into steering signals. The mission waypoints may or may not have an auto_continue flag set. All the intermediate waypoints have this flag set. If a waypoint with auto_continue = 0 is reached, the path follower is paused until a new target mission waypoint (usually the next one) is received from the gRCS.

Figure 27. BIKE Path-Control

- **Robot Control**

The robot control was implemented following the description already given in section 3.2.3 in D5.2. Some slight modifications to the navigation field were implemented in order to allow going backwards and to improve the stability of the control system.

The navigation field generates a reference orientation for every point in a 2D plane (the projection of the target point to the robot plane). The controller uses the reference orientation as well as the local curvature of the navigation field to generate a steering reference guiding the vehicle along the field lines towards the waypoint.

Figure 28. BIKE Navigation Field for Waypoint approach

3.3.2 HYBRID

The HYBRID robot consists of a UAV and its SATELLITE robot.

The robotic engine of the HYBRID platform has many similarities with the AERO-CAM platform. In terms of navigation sensors, both platforms have the same sensors, although using mirrors with the LiDAR to increase their vertical field of view. Despite having a different LiDAR configuration, both platforms use the same localization algorithm.

As for the mission manager and integration with gRCS, the software is the same with minor modifications, such as the number of commands implemented by each platform. It is therefore that in this section we are not going to describe again the main blocks that have already been done in AERO-CAM and this platform shares.

- **Ouster LiDAR driver**

The Ouster LiDAR in the aerial vehicle needs a driver module to obtain a point cloud from the raw data in the same manner as AERO-CAM. However, there is an important difference due to its configuration. There are two leaning mirrors in front of the LiDAR, allowing part of the laser beams to point up and down thanks to the reflection. Therefore, this configuration avoids the blind spots above and below the LiDAR sensor.

The driver needs to transform the range data of the sensor into a spatial point cloud. Thus, it is necessary to take into account the mirrors' pose and the laser beam angles. The driver provides a full point cloud of all the environment, making the mirror configuration transparent for the user.

Hence, this module publishes the same ROS messages as the original one including the full point cloud in a *sensor_msgs/PointCloud2* message and a status message to inform of the current sensor status. In addition, it also publishes another ROS topic with an array of indexes indicating which points of the full point cloud are produced by the mirror reflection. These indexes can be used for visualization purposes or to isolate the reflected part of the point cloud.

Figure 29. Sample point cloud from the LiDAR with leaning mirrors (in red the reflected points above and below the sensor)

- **SATELLITE System**

The satellite crawler is equipped with a dead-reckoning based localization system, which makes use of a mesh model of the environment similar to the BIKE crawler. The main difference is that the satellite does not have any means of absolute positioning along the longitudinal pipe section. Therefore, all the pose feedback it provides is relative to the initial placement location (i.e. the landing spot of the UAV).

From the operators' point of view, the satellite is considered an ultrasound sensor with some mobility and control. Control is entirely based on operator input. The measurement locations can be captured in 3D with respect to the landing point of the UAV. The environment model used by the satellite control software, the pipe section, will be retrieved from the data layer prior to the mission and loaded based on the Inspection Plan Identifier (*plan_id*).

The satellite is communicating over an Ethernet link with the control interface. The link is provided by the UAV. Otherwise, the satellite is independent of the UAV and the gRCS.

4. Integration Validation in Controlled Environments

In this section, we will describe the integration and demonstrate the integration test performed between the gRCS and the robotic platforms. For simplicity and document extension, we will show the integration of one of the platforms of each of the typologies: aerial, ground, and crawlers/hybrids. All integration tests have been performed with the software developed for the different robotic engines described in Section 3. The validation tests have been performed in a laboratory and/or controlled environments. For greater veracity, simulations of the movement of the robotic platforms have been performed with software and/or hardware in the loop when it has been physically possible to perform them. For these simulations, the same software developed has been used.

Given the number of robotic platforms developed in this project, a common plan for validating their integration with the gRCS has been created. In this plan, the necessary functionalities have been isolated and specific common testing requirements have been established. In addition, these functionalities have been ordered incrementally according to their level of importance, so it is important to complete them in an ordered manner for the correct validation of the system.

The functionalities to be validated on which we have focused are:

- **Heartbeat:** the basic capability to make a connection between the gRCS and the robotic platform.
- **Telemetry:** be able to send position and orientation information to the gRCS, as well as status text messages.
- **Navigation:** be able to receive a list of waypoints, process it, and execute it giving feedback to the gRCS on the progress of the mission. Be able to change the current waypoint at the request of the gRCS.
- **Commands:** be able to process and execute commands sent from the gRCS.

For the validation of these functionalities, all partners have been provided with separate executables for each functionality that work just like the gRCS. This has greatly facilitated the validation, as all platforms have the same conditions in the tests to be executed.

The step-by-step validation plans have been as follows:

1 - Implement Heartbeat protocol	
Validation Requirements	Description
1	Install the " <i>piloting-mavsdk</i> " library, and in case of using ROS also the node " <i>piloting-mavsdk-ros</i> "
2	Configure "local_system_id" and "local_component_id" with the values assigned to each partner
3	Launch your system executable with " <i>piloting-mavsdk</i> " implemented

4	Launch the "piloting_gcs_heartbeat_example" executable that simulates gRCS
5	Verify that both systems have been able to find each other and are communicating correctly

Table 17. Validation plan for the Heartbeat protocol

2 - Implement Telemetry protocol	
Validation Requirements	Description
1	Have implemented the Heartbeat protocol
2	Have a system that provides the position and orientation of the robotic vehicle (simulator or real measurements)
3	Develop software that takes the position and orientation of the robotic vehicle and sends it to the gRCS
4	Develop software that sends some status messages (INFO, WARNING and ERROR) to the gRCS
5	Launch your system executable with "piloting-mavsdk" implemented
6	Launch the "piloting_gcs_telemetry_example" executable that simulates gRCS
7	Verify that the position and orientation of the robotic vehicle are correctly received, as well as the status messages sent

Table 18. Validation plan for the Telemetry protocol

3 - Implement Navigation protocol	
Validation Requirements	Description
1	Have implemented the Heartbeat protocol
2	Have a system that can handle a list of waypoints and can command the real robot or simulator the movements necessary to reach these waypoints sequentially
3	Develop software that implements the receipt of a list of waypoints from the gRCS
4	Develop software that implements the reception of the "set_current_inspection_item" message from the gRCS, and then commands the real robot or simulator the movements to reach the waypoint indicated in this message
5	Develop software that implements the sending of navigation progress (that is, when a waypoint has been reached and when the target waypoint changes)
6	Launch your system executable with "piloting-mavsdk" implemented
7	Adapt the executable "piloting_gcs_inspection_example" with the list of waypoints that you want to receive in the robotic system, and then launch this executable that simulates the gRCS
8	Verify that the list of waypoints is correctly received, the robot navigates satisfactorily and also that the navigation progress is correctly received in the gRCS simulator

Table 19. Validation plan for the Navigation protocol

4 - Implement Command protocol	
Validation Requirements	Description
1	Have implemented the Heartbeat protocol
2	Develop software that implements receiving a command with a specific action, checking if the action is compatible with your system, and responding with an ACK message
3	Launch your system executable with <i>"piloting-mavsdk"</i> implemented
4	Adapt the <i>"piloting_gcs_command_example"</i> executable to send a command with a compatible action and then a command with an incompatible action, and then launch this executable that simulates gRCS
5	Verify that the commands are received correctly and that the expected ACK responses are displayed in the gRCS simulator

Table 20. Validation plan for the Command protocol

The following subsections describe the tasks devoted to testing these validation plans for each type of robotic vehicle.

4.1 Aerial Robots

The validation of the aerial robot's integration has been performed using the AERO-CAM platform. For this task, the software architecture of its robotic engine, described in Section 3.1, has been tested. The integration tests were first performed using the executables provided for each of the protocols separately. This has been especially helpful during the development and debugging of the robotic engine. Once validated, the gRCS was used to check the integration again and illustrate the result.

These tests have used both the real platform and data recorded during flights (ROSbag files) that facilitated the repetition of tests during development. For the navigation tests of this integration, DJI's autopilot simulator with hardware-in-the-loop was used. This has allowed performing many experiments in the gRCS with the real system, but without having to physically fly, having the same behavior.

The integrations of the different communication protocols introduced above are shown below:

Heartbeat protocol integration

The gRCS is able to communicate with the Robotic System via MAVSDK-ROS. The system communication options can be changed in the gRCS using the dialog shown in Figure 30-left. When all this information is correctly configured, the operator can connect to the robotic system using the connect tool button on the upper side. When this button is clicked, a confirmation dialog as the following pops up, as shown in Figure 30-right.

Figure 30. Communication options dialog (left) and connection confirmation dialog (right)

If the “OK” button is pressed, the gRCS will try to connect to the robotic system using this communication configuration. If the connection is properly made, a message will appear in the console widget reporting on this event. If the connection cannot be established, a pop-up message is shown. Both results are shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31. Successful connection messages (top), and connection error pop-up (bottom)

Telemetry protocol integration

Once the connection has been established, the gRCS starts receiving the telemetry data. This telemetry data can be visualized with the telemetry widget that represents general information about the execution of the inspection, the NED position, NED velocity, attitude and angular velocity of the robotic vehicle (see Figure 32-left). Moreover, the UAV position is represented in the 3D visualizer as an axis marker in Figure 32-right.

Figure 32. Telemetry widget (left), and UAV position axis in the 3D viewer (right)

Additionally, the text status messages sent by the robotic vehicle can be visualized in the gRCS. When the gRCS receives a text status message, it is displayed in the console widget.

Navigation protocol integration

When a planned path is created by the operator in the gRCS, it can be uploaded to the robotic vehicle using the “Upload Waypoint List” button from the “Robots Control” widget.

Figure 33. Upload waypoint list button

Figure 34. Planned path

When the “Upload Waypoint List” button is pressed, the planned path is sent to the Mission Manager submodule via MAVSDK_ROS, the robotic vehicle’s Mission Manager will check if the format of the waypoint list received is valid. If the format is not valid or the parsing of the waypoint list cannot be carried out, a warning message informing about this event will be sent by the Mission Manager. An example of such a warning message is shown in Figure 35-top. If

the waypoint list is parsed and uploaded to the robotic vehicle successfully, an information message is displayed in the console widget. As it can be seen in Figure 35-bottom, the size of the general waypoint list is 7, while the size of the generated specific waypoint list is 18.

Figure 35. Upload Waypoint List warning message (top), and successful upload messages (bottom)

Moreover, the line connecting the waypoints changes its color to green whenever the waypoint list is uploaded correctly to the robotic vehicle, as it is shown in the following figure.

Figure 36. Uploaded waypoint list

Command protocol integration

When the connection is established, the gRCS is able to download the high-level actions supported by the robotic vehicle using the “Robots Control” widget. When the “Download High Level Actions” button is pressed, a list of high-level actions appears in the corresponding widget. An example of the high-level actions supported by the AERO-CAM UAV is shown in Figure 37-right.

Figure 37. Download High-Level Actions button (left) and example of high-level actions (right)

If the execution of a high-level action wants to be commanded by the gRCS operator, the associated button might be pressed; at that moment, a dialog will appear with the information about the high-level action. The operator might complete the information about the parameters of the command associated with that high-level action. An example of this dialog is shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38. Command parameters dialog for Take Off high-level action

When the “OK” button is pressed, the command associated with the high-level action is sent to the robotic vehicle. The robotic vehicle checks if the command is supported and if the parameters associated with such command are valid. If the request of the command to the robotic system is not successful, a pop-up is shown, such as the one in Figure 39-top. Moreover, a warning text status message is received with the information of the failure, shown in the console (Figure 39-bottom).

Figure 39. Send Command error pop-up (top) and console messages (bottom)

If the parameters are valid and the robotic vehicle can carry out the requested command, an information text status message is received as shown in Figure 40, and the execution of the command is performed.


```
Console
[15:22:08] (INFO) [executeCommand] Command received of type: MAV_CMD_NAV_TAKEOFF
[15:22:08] (INFO) [sendTakeOffService] take off
[15:22:08] (INFO) Sucessfully sent command to vehicle
[15:22:08] (INFO) [executeCommnad] Command execution successfull of type: MAV_CMD_NAV_TAKEOFF
```

Figure 40. Send Command information message

4.2 Ground Robots

Related to the integration of ground robots with the gRCS, and as explained in Section 2, most of the work has dealt with the MAVSDK wrapper for ROS. Besides, specific pieces of software were created or modified specifically for this validation procedure. An iterative methodology has been followed according to the integration plan described at the beginning of Section 4.

The different modifications have been validated in subsequent stages, considering tests on top of the Heartbeat, Telemetry, Navigation and Command protocols. From the beginning, and thanks to the common ROS framework of Robotnik's robots, we could always test the robot behavior and software response thanks to a controlled scenario in a simulation environment based on Gazebo, a simulator that allows to rapidly test algorithms.

Heartbeat protocol integration

The heartbeat protocol was tested easily thanks to the example provided in the MAVSDK library. This basic test allowed us to verify that both ends of the communication link were able to find each other and were communicating correctly.

Telemetry protocol integration

While the heartbeat protocol was integrated seamlessly, modifications were needed to support the types of telemetry messages initially included in the MAVSDK-ROS wrapper.

Originally, two different message subscribers were present to send and receive telemetry messages to and from the gRCS, one for pose messages including position and orientation (geometry_msgs/PoseStamped) and another one for velocity messages including linear and angular velocities (geometry_msgs/TwistStamped). However, Robotnik's system group all this

information into a single message (nav_msgs/Odometry) that contains both the pose and the velocity of the robot.

	Message Contents
std_msgs/Header header	uint32 seq time stamp string frame_id
geometry_msgs/Pose pose	geometry_msgs/Point point geometry_msgs/Quaternion orientation

Table 21. geometry_msgs/PoseStamped message

	Message Contents
std_msgs/Header header	uint32 seq time stamp string frame_id
geometry_msgs/Twist twist	geometry_msgs/Vector3 linear geometry_msgs/Vector3 angular

Table 22. geometry_msgs/TwistStamped message

	Message Contents
std_msgs/Header header	uint32 seq time stamp string frame_id
string child_frame_id	
geometry_msgs/PoseWithCovariance pose	geometry_msgs/Pose pose float64[36] covariance
geometry_msgs/TwistWithCovariance twist	geometry_msgs/Twist twist float64[36] covariance

Table 23. nav_msgs/Odometry message

The support for other types of ROS-native odometry messages was then added to MAVSDK-ROS once this test was performed and verified, as Figure 41 shows.

```

mmillet: ~/piloting-mavsdk/examples/build/piloting_telemetry
mmillet@mmillet: ~/piloting-mavsdk/examples/build/piloting_telemetry
roll_rad_s: 0
pitch_rad_s: 0
yaw_rad_s: -0.329903185367584
}
}
PositionVelocityNed received:
position_velocity_ned:
{
  system_id: 1
  component_id: 25
  stamp_ms: 1438095
  position: position_ned:
  {
    north_m: 0.341831658263779
    east_m: 5.52042198181152
    down_m: -0
  }
  velocity: velocity_ned:
  {
    north_m_s: -0.00243023899383843
    east_m_s: 0.0504494905471802
    down_m_s: -0
  }
}
}
Attitude received:
attitude:
{
  system_id: 1
  component_id: 25
  stamp_ms: 1438095
  quaternion_angle: quaternion:
  {
    w: 0.212717726826668
    x: 0.000636658456642181
    y: 0.00296274200081825
    z: 0.977169014987946
  }
  angular_velocity: angular_velocity_body:
  {
    roll_rad_s: 0
    pitch_rad_s: 0
    yaw_rad_s: -0.361351728439331
  }
}
}

```

Figure 41. Telemetry messages received via MAVSDK wrapper

Navigation and Command protocol integration

On the other hand, a full test concerning both Navigation and Command protocols was conceived, especially due to the fact that the latter is an extension of the former. For this validation, we just issued an existing command in our Command Manager linked to the command and parameters communicated through MAVSDK. In this case, the command consisted in sending the robot to a specific waypoint location:

- The navigation protocol integration was validated by manually sending the robot different waypoints.
- The command protocol integration was validated through the action “go to waypoint” executed on the robot.

It was successfully tested that the simulated robot could:

1. Receive the message through MAVSDK.
2. Parse the waypoint, command and parameters, and generate a mission readable by the Command Manager.
3. Sequence the actions in a proper way, navigating and performing the command.
4. Provide feedback on sequence status.

Figure 42 shows a sequence of the simulated test. In the beginning, the waypoint is manually selected using RViz, the graphical user interface provided by the ROS framework for visualization purposes. Then, the robot, after processing the waypoint message and the action command, starts to turn and traverse the world towards the commanded waypoint, finally reaching it.

Figure 42. The sequence of robot actions for validating navigation and command protocols. The waypoint (pink arrow) is sent, then the robot moves towards the commanded waypoint

Regarding autonomous functionalities dealing with robot navigation, the detection and avoidance of obstacles have also been validated in this simulated scenario. As it can be seen in Figure 43, when there is an obstacle between the commanded waypoint and the robot's current location, the robot automatically calculates a path free of obstacles for reaching the waypoint. This is a basic test that will need further refinement in subsequent stages of the integration process.

Figure 43. Simulation environment for testing the integration of Robotnik's ground robots

The same workflow has been followed to test the integration of the manipulation-specific autonomous functionalities. The evaluation and iterative tests are performed in a simulated environment consisting of a Gazebo simulation, including the robotic manipulator and the same state machine to be deployed on the real robot. The latter is implemented as a reusable and modular wrapper of the smach Python library³. As both the logic and state machine do not change between simulated and real tests, and this is the bridge between the gRCS and the robotic engine, we expect little to no modifications during real robot deployment.

4.3 Crawlers and Hybrid Robots

The test setup used for the integration testing consists of a lab mockup and the BIKE robot, equipped with standard 3D LOC LiDAR-based localization. In Figure 45 and Figure 46 a very basic test, moving the robot just about half a meter forward, is shown. The received telemetry data from the two positions are shown in Table 24.

A mesh model of the lab mockup was used and a dummy *plan_id* (the one from the gRCS example: 98654321) was associated with this model.

First, the BIKE was manually moved to a total of 7 locations. On each location, the pose of the robot was stored to be later used as waypoints.

Figure 44 shows the test setup and the path that was driven when storing the waypoints.

³ <http://wiki.ros.org/smach>

Figure 44. Left: BIKE in mockup environment; Right: path test

Heartbeat protocol integration

The gRCS example was used to verify that the Bridge Program connected correctly.

Telemetry protocol integration

The BIKE was moved in the mockup with telemetry running. The output on the gRCS example code was compared to the actual location and orientation. In Figure 45 and Figure 46, a very basic test, moving the robot just about half a meter forward is shown.

When looking at the received telemetry data from the two positions as shown in Table 24, a movement of 0.472 m in the EAST direction was received.

Figure 45. BIKE telemetry test starting position

Figure 46. BIKE telemetry end position

	Position 1	Position 2	Delta [m]
north_m	-0.0266	-0.00469	0.02191
east_m	0.0726	0.5449	0.4723
down_m	0.799	0.8051	0.0061

Table 24. BIKE Forward Motion Telemetry Data

Navigation protocol integration

The provided example was modified to parse a JSON file containing the robot poses which would serve as mission waypoints. All waypoints (except for the final one) were sent with

$auto_continue=0$, so the robot would not stop. When invoked the waypoint list was transmitted to the robot control and the path follower successfully guided the BIKE from waypoint to waypoint.

The waypoints were also visualized on the robot control GUI in order to verify consistency. A video was recorded of the experiment as well as of the robot control GUI visualization. Figure 47 shows stills from the two videos.

Figure 47. Extract from BIKE visualization during the experiment as well as from the video recorded

A comparison (overlay) was made between the original manually driven path from which the milestones were generated, and the path recorded during the experiment. Figure 48 shows a comparison of the path driven manually and the resulting path from the autonomous operation. In the overlay, it is clearly visible that the autonomously operating robot takes a shorter path and how the two paths match at the waypoint locations.

Figure 48. Comparison of the manually driven path and automated path completed by the BIKE (Left: path completed by joystick handling the robot, waypoints stored. Center: path completed by robot autonomously. Right: overlay where the green line is the manual path and crosshairs the waypoints.

Command protocol integration

To verify that the commands sent by the operator on the gRCS truly reach the robot control, a modified version of the gRCS example was used. Keypresses of numbers triggered sending the following commands:

- 1: MAV_CMD_DO_SET_MODE (“PLACE_ROBOT”)
- 2: MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE (“PAUSE”)
- 3: MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE (“RESUME”)
- 4: MAV_CMD_IMAGE_START_CAPTURE (“CAPTURE”)

On the State Machine, it was verified if the correct corresponding action was triggered by each command. The reactions were the following:

- 1: MAV_CMD_DO_SET_MODE (“PLACE_ROBOT”) → start a timer, wait 2 minutes max to either receive confirmation of placement by the operator or acknowledge failed
- 2: MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE (“PAUSE”) → set the autopilot to state “paused” start timer to observe if the state machine actually changed state
- 3: MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE (“RESUME”) → set the autopilot to state “active” start timer to observe if the state machine actually changed state
- 4: MAV_CMD_IMAGE_START_CAPTURE (“CAPTURE”) → an image capture is triggered on the robot control. If the user accepts within 2 minutes it will be acknowledged successful, otherwise as unsuccessful

4.4 Other common aspects

This subsection deals with commonalities for the remaining aspects common to all robotic vehicles that are managed through the gRCS, which were not considered in this initial integration validation process: alarms and checklists. The reason behind not including these is that we wanted to focus on the more complex protocols, since once the communication of telemetry, navigation and commands were validated, adding these two aspects is trivial in the sense that they consist in a different type of message. In the following, we describe the workflow for both the alarms and the checklists for the robotic vehicles.

Alarms

The alarms of the robotic vehicle might be downloaded using the “Robots Control” widget.

Figure 49. Download Alarm list button

If the download of the alarm list cannot be completed, a warning pop-up will be displayed. Moreover, a warning message will be shown in the console widget.

Figure 50. Download Alarm list error pop-up (top), and console warning message (bottom)

However, if downloading the alarm list has been successful, an information pop-up will be displayed.

Figure 51. Alarm list successful download message

Furthermore, the alarm list will appear in the “Robot Alarms” widget, as it is shown in Figure 52.

Figure 52. Alarm List Widget

During the execution of the inspection, the gRCS might receive the errors, warnings, and status messages of each of the alarms in the alarm list. There are four levels of alarm status represented by four different colors, as specified in Table 25.

Alarm status level	Color
Unknown	Gray
OK	Green
Warning	Yellow
Error	Red

Table 25. Alarm levels and corresponding colors

An example of the alarm list widget during the execution of an inspection is shown in Figure 53.

The screenshot shows a window titled "Robot Alarms" with a green "COMMS STATUS" bar at the top. Below it is an "Alarm List" table with the following data:

Status	ID	Name	Errors	Warns
Red	0	Alarm 1	3	5
Yellow	1	Alarm 2	0	4
Green	2	Alarm 3	0	1
Grey	3	Alarm 4		

Figure 53. Alarm List Widget during an inspection

Checklist

The checklist might be downloaded using the Robots Control widget.

Figure 54. Download Checklist button

When the “Download CheckList” button is pressed, the gRCS requests the robotic vehicle the checklist. If the checklist cannot be downloaded, a warning pop-up message will be shown to the operator. Besides, a warning message will be displayed in the console reporting on this event, as Figure 55 shows.

Figure 55. Download Checklist error pop-up (top), and console warning message (bottom)

However, if the download of the checklist has been carried out successfully, an information message as the following will be displayed.

Figure 56. Successful Checklist download information message

Using the Checklist Tool button, a dialog with the checklist will pop up. The check status of each item can be editable using the corresponding checkbox. If the operator clicks the “OK” button, a confirmation dialog with the current check status of the item will be displayed.

Figure 57. Checklist dialog

Figure 58. Checklist confirmation dialog

5. Conclusions

This document covers the efforts towards the integration of the wide variety of robotic vehicles in PILOTING project. The generalization of the interface (gRCS) to such a diversity of robotic vehicles is possible thanks to the robotic engines, which incorporate a high level of autonomy. A detailed description of the software developed for the integration of the gRCS with each of the platforms is included. In addition, validation experiments in controlled environments have also been presented, showing the communications between these two components of the PILOTING I&M platform.

Integration and testing are very time-consuming and costly tasks when it comes to developing autonomous robotic systems, because the robotic vehicle must be fully operational before carrying out experiments, a space for testing must be accessible, and specifically qualified staff must be available (e.g. safety pilot in the case of aerial robots). The proposed integration strategy based on protocols with incremental complexity has proven to be successful, given the variety of robotic platforms, the limited time, and travel restrictions (due to covid-19) to carry out the integration tasks.

Simulation environments have been very useful for testing the behavior and integration of different modules, especially those related to navigation and motion planning. Even though simulations are still limited in order to provide accurate information regarding real-world scenarios or behaviors of actual systems, they have been useful to test the various developments in controlled scenarios.

Besides, providing a stable version of the gRCS to the partners integrating robotic vehicles has allowed testing additional functionalities for the validation of communications in both ways, from the beginning of the mission until the collection of information after the inspection.

This has been the result of the first iteration of the robotic systems integration. Following these activities, the integration with the rest of the modules of the PILOTING I&M platform will be carried out. After all these integration works are finished (WP7), the first iteration of the large-scale pilot demonstrations will be performed (WP8), where lessons learned will be extracted towards the second development cycle of PILOTING project.